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Environment-Driven Requirements-Based Testing

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Abstract

A software's feature descriptions are a medium for an end-user to determine how a software's particular function works. During software development, a requirements engineer will formulate a software's requirements stating exactly what the software-to-be should do. In this research, I have created an algorithm that inputs software feature descriptions and outputs any feature descriptions containing insufficient natural language based on my hypothesized linguistic rules. After manually creating a data set from release notes published on Zoom's website and tagging whether the feature descriptions contained an oracle or not, the algorithm was run using the data set. The results show that my linguistic rules can be used sufficiently to alert requirements engineers if natural language in certain feature descriptions may need to be altered before handing feature descriptions over to a software tester to create requirements-based software tests.

1 Introduction

In requirements engineering (RE), software requirements are defined as stakeholders needs and desires. A stakeholder is someone who has stake in the project, whether that be a software developer or end user of the software. Software requirements are defined as an entailment of the environment and the specifications: $E, S \vdash R$ [1]. The environment the software is running (E) and the specifications that the developers use to create software (S) are combined to fulfill the requirements (R). Creating software that does not meet the correct requirements can have devastating financial, security, or even mortal impacts depending on the application.

1.1 Problem

The single most challenging part of creating software is deciding precisely what to make. No other part of the conceptual work is as difficult as formulating detailed technical requirements, no other part of the work can cripple the resulting product if done incorrectly, and no other part is as difficult to rectify later than having deficient requirements [2]. It is very important that the requirements engineers, software developers, software testers, and end users all have the same expectation of how a software's particular function performs. However, this is very difficult to accomplish. This research project helps address this problem by creating an algorithm that uses linguistic rules to determine if a software's feature descriptions contain sufficient natural language (NL) to derive an oracle from it.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 Requirements-Based Testing

Requirements-Based Testing (RBT) is the process of writing software tests based on the software's requirements. This was introduced by Skoković and Skoković as a solution for most software projects failing to achieve schedule and budget goals. The requirements-based testing workflow is demonstrated in Figure 1 below and shows the extra step to fix requirements if logical

test cases fail. The results showed that requirements-based testing is an effective method at reducing the number of problematic requirements [3]. Requirements-based testing is now standard practice in industry, yet still time-consuming. Because of this, and since requirements are written in natural language, natural language processing can be used to help aid the refinement of natural language within requirements.

Figure 1: Requirements-based testing process flow (adapted from Skoković and Skoković [3])

2.2 Natural Language Processing

Natural Language Processing (NLP) refers to the branch of computer science (specifically artificial intelligence) related to giving computers the ability to understand text in the same way that human beings can [4]. The top three techniques used for NLP-assisted software testing are part-of-speech tagging, dependency parsing, and keyword checking [5]. In this research, dependency parsing and part-of-speech tagging are used. Dependency parsing is the process of examining the dependencies between phrases in a sentence, while part-of-speech tagging is annotating what part of speech each word in a sentence is (noun, adjective, verb, adverb, etc.).

3 Project Methodology

3.1 Project Objectives

The main objectives of this research project are to:

1. Examine and analyze part-of-speech and dependency relations in existing software feature descriptions.
2. Develop an algorithm that takes feature descriptions as an input and raises different flags based on incompleteness, ambiguity, or any other requirements issues.
3. Report and analyze results of the algorithm and provide recommendations for future work.

3.2 Research Approach

3.2.1 Bug Searching

The first step in this research was searching for bugs on [Zoom's software](#). In this sense, a bug was found if a conducted user test on a certain feature of the software did not perform how I expected based on my interpretation of the feature description published on [Zoom's release notes webpage](#) (for Windows).

3.2.2 Documenting Findings & Testability

After finding and testing feature descriptions of interest, the results were documented through screenshots and listing testing steps [See Appendix]. A list containing 12 feature descriptions of interest was compiled. This list of feature descriptions was first ranked in terms of subjectivity of the natural language and the resulting tests conducted. The feature descriptions with the most precise interpretations were ranked the highest, while the feature descriptions with loose interpretations were ranked the lowest. Some feature descriptions of interest were found to be untestable due to subscription limitations. Any feature descriptions that were untestable were ranked lowest. After rankings were completed, the feature descriptions in this list were then categorized by type of requirements issue. The categories for this list were incomplete natural language, ambiguous natural language, and incorrect natural language. Screenshots of testing and a list of testing steps were then added to the document for each feature description. The final step was determining a cut-off line in which the verification of each feature description ranked above the cut-off line would have only one human interpretation. This step was crucial in formulating the linguistic rules for determining if a feature description contains a testing oracle.

3.2.3 Dataset Formulation & Breakdown

The dataset used in this research was created using the feature descriptions published by Zoom from the months of February 2023 to August 2022. It is important to note there are no feature descriptions for October 2022. This provided 180 feature descriptions of Zoom's software features. As part of my research, I manually read each feature description and determined if each feature description contained an oracle in relation to software testing. I found there to be 45 feature descriptions that did not contain an oracle and 135 feature descriptions that did contain

an oracle. This is a good indication that the feature descriptions published by Zoom are a good standard for feature descriptions from a requirements standpoint. The dataset breakdown can be found below in Figure 2. This dataset was then used to evaluate the effectiveness of my linguistic algorithm.

Figure 2: The dataset’s breakdown of feature descriptions that do and do not contain an oracle.

3.2.4 Algorithm Formulation (Sentence Level)

After completing the work in section 3.2.2, I then ran the 12 feature descriptions through [CoreNLP](#) to view results on part-of-speech tagging and dependency parsing. At this point, I had a few months of feature descriptions for my dataset completed and ran these through CoreNLP, comparing the results of feature descriptions with no oracle vs. feature descriptions that contained an oracle.

Figure 3: CoreNLP output for part-of-speech tagging on a feature description.

Figure 4: CoreNLP output for dependency parsing on a feature description.

Universal Stanford Dependencies [6] helped me better understand the dependency parsing results from feature descriptions. Core arguments are a grouping of 6 different universal dependencies: nominal subjects (nsubj), objects (obj), indirect objects (iobj), clausal subjects (csubj), clausal complements (ccomp), and open clausal complements (xcomp).

	Nominals	Clauses
Core arguments	<u>nsubj.</u> <u>obj.</u> <u>iobj.</u>	<u>csubj.</u> <u>ccomp.</u> <u>xcomp.</u>

Figure 5: Chart of universal dependency tags of core arguments (adapted from de Marneffe et. al [6]).

After analyzing the results from feature descriptions ran through CoreNLP, I was able to identify two main distinguishers between feature descriptions that do contain an oracle vs. feature descriptions that do not contain oracle. These two distinguishers were core argument count and verb count. Using these counts, I formulated the following rules for my linguistic algorithm:

Rule 1: If a sentence has less than 2 core arguments, the sentence shall be marked as not containing an oracle.

Rule 2: If a sentence has less than 3 verbs, the sentence shall be marked as not containing an oracle.

My hypothesis behind rule 1 is that there must be two core arguments: one describing the user's interaction with the software and one describing the oracle taking place. My hypothesis behind rule 2 is that there must be three verbs: one verb describing the action of the user's software interaction, one verb describing the action of the oracle occurring, and one verb connecting these two actions together.

3.2.5 Algorithm Aggregation (Feature-Description Level)

Since feature descriptions can contain multiple sentences, I needed to use my linguistic rules at a sentence-level and aggregate them to a feature-description level. To do this, the rules are still implemented at a sentence-level, and the results of any flags that are caught by my linguistic rules are then combined in an or logic diagram to get a result. In other words, if either Rule1 or Rule2 marks any sentence in a feature description as not having an oracle, my algorithm's output says that the feature description does not contain an oracle. This was decided on to keep recall high with the understanding that precision would fall under a mid-range.

Figure 6: Logic diagram of my linguistic algorithm's aggregated rules for a feature description that contains 2 sentences.

3.3 Results and Evaluation

After aggregating my linguistic rules into a Python program and importing 180 Zoom feature descriptions as text files, the results were compiled. The work by Hayes et. al was used to judge the algorithm's performance for recall and precision.

Measure	Acceptable	Good	Excellent
Recall	60% - 69%	70% - 79%	80% - 100%
Precision	20% - 29%	30% - 49%	50% - 100%

Figure 7: Table of metric ranges [7] Adapted from Hayes, et. al.

A breakdown of the results by month is found below in Figure 8, showing the recall and precision scores. All months had between 24-29 feature descriptions besides December 2022, having 44 feature descriptions. Overall, the recall against the dataset is in the excellent range while the precision against the dataset is at the very top off the acceptable range.

Metric	Feb 2023	Jan 2023	Dec 2022	Nov 2022	Sep 2022	Aug 2022	Overall
Recall	83.3%	66.7%	83.3%	88.9%	90.9%	100.0%	86.67%
Precision	25.0%	11.8%	30.3%	34.8%	43.5%	25.0%	29.55%

Figure 8: Monthly breakdown of the algorithm's results when ran against the dataset of 180 Zoom feature descriptions.

A categorization of the results is found below in Figure 9, showing the amount of each category from the results of my algorithm. The true positives and true negatives totaled 81 out of 180 feature descriptions, which indicates my algorithm predicted 45% of true outcomes in the dataset. The high number of false positives and low number of false negatives reflects the intentions of my algorithm's rules keeping recall high while sacrificing precision for the sake of trying to flag all problematic feature descriptions as not containing an oracle.

Result Category	Count (out of 180)
True Positive	39
False Positive	93
True Negative	42
False Negative	6

Figure 9: Categorization of the algorithm's results when ran against the dataset of 180 Zoom feature descriptions.

3.4 Resources Used

The resources used for this research project are listed below:

1. [CoreNLP](#) – A natural language processing toolkit by Stanford used for dependency parsing and part-of-speech tagging.
2. [Stanza](#) – A python interface to CoreNLP.
3. [PyCharm](#) – A Python IDE used to write my code.
4. [Excel](#) – Spreadsheet software used to store data and create graphs & charts.

3.5 Project Timeline

This research project was conducted over the Fall 2022 and Spring 2023 semesters at the University of Cincinnati. A Gantt chart outlining tasks and timelines is found below.

Task ID	Task Name	Start Date	End Date	Duration (Weeks)	9/12/2022	9/19/2022	9/26/2022	10/3/2022	10/10/2022	10/17/2022	10/24/2022	10/31/2022	11/7/2022	11/14/2022	11/21/2022	11/28/2022	12/5/2022	12/12/2022	12/19/2022	12/26/2022	1/2/2023	1/9/2023	1/16/2023	1/23/2023	1/30/2023	2/6/2023	2/13/2023	2/20/2023	2/27/2023	3/6/2023	3/13/2023	3/20/2023	4/3/2023	4/10/2023	4/17/2023	4/24/2023		
					T01	Background Research & Topic Introduction	9/15/2022	9/25/2022	2	█	█																											
T02	Literature Research	9/19/2022	11/27/2022	6		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
T03	Literature Review	10/3/2022	11/20/2022	7			█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
T04	Data Analysis on 123 Zoom feature descriptions	10/3/2022	11/13/2022	6				█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
T05	Project Specification First Draft	10/10/2022	10/28/2022	3					█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
T06	Bug searching on Zoom	11/21/2022	11/28/2022	6									█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
T07	End-of-Semester Presentation	11/21/2022	11/28/2022	2										█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
T08	Bug Testing on "Problem" Features	1/9/2023	1/29/2023	3																			█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
T09	Rank "Problem" Features and Establish Cutoff Line	1/23/2023	2/5/2023	2																																		
T10	Formulate and Evaluate Initial Algorithm Rules	2/6/2023	2/19/2023	2																																		
T11	Formulate and Evaluate Revised Algorithm Rules	2/20/2023	3/12/2023	3																																		
T12	Midterm Presentation	3/6/2023	3/10/2023	1																																		
T13	Finalize Algorithm Rules	3/13/2023	4/2/2023	2																																		
T14	Evaluate Algorithm on additional dataset(s)	3/20/2023	4/2/2023	1																																		
T15	Senior Design Expo	4/6/2023	4/6/2023	1																																		
T16	Final Report	4/3/2023	4/24/2023	2																																		
T17	Final Presentation	4/17/2023	4/21/2023	1																																		

Figure 10: Gantt chart highlighting the tasks and timeline of this research project.

4 Conclusion

The field of requirements engineering is constantly coming up with different techniques to solve real-world problems in the software development lifecycle. Running a software-to-be’s feature descriptions through an algorithm before designing software tests is a part of these solutions. My research has shown great promise that this can effectively be done to verify that a software’s requirements are complete, correct, and unambiguous. Once these requirements are met, software test cases can then be created to verify that an oracle pertaining to these criteria is present.

Future work in this research can include implementing my linguistic rules into a machine learning algorithm, having a ranking system for these linguistic rules and flags, adding additional linguistic rules to the algorithm, and expanding the dataset to use software feature descriptions from other sources. Implementing these recommendations into future research should be able to increase the recall and precision of the algorithm and help achieve the overall goal of making software better by uncovering natural language discrepancies.

Data Availability

The dataset used in this research is available in the Zenodo repository, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7868611>.

5 Appendix

This appendix contains my ranked problematic feature descriptions based on natural language clarity and contains an established cut-off line.

1. **Description:** When users view an upcoming meeting in either the Home page or the Meetings tab, the meeting host’s name provides the host’s profile card on hover. An option to chat directly with the host is also provided next to their name. If the host is not already a contact, the option to add them as a contact is provided.

Category: **Incorrect NL** – Profile card shows when hovering on profile picture; doesn’t show when hovering over name

Source: [Highlighted Link](#)

Release: August 22, 2022 version 5.11.9 (8040)

Testing Steps:

- I. Go to “Home” tab on Zoom client.
- II. Hover over host’s name on an upcoming meeting.

Figure 11 - Profile card doesn't appear when hovering over host's name

Figure 12 - Profile card appears when hovering over host's profile picture

- III. Repeat for the “Meetings” tab on Zoom client

Figure 13 - Profile card doesn't appear when hovering over host's name

Figure 14 - Profile card appears when hovering over host's profile picture

2. **Description:** When variations of “Happy Anniversary” are used in Zoom Chat, a celebration of raining Tada emojis will rain down in the chat window.

Category: **Ambiguous NL** – Chat type is not specified in the feature description (Team Chat vs. Meeting Chat)

Source: [Highlighted Link](#)

Release: June 20, 2022 version 5.11.0 (6569)

Testing Steps:

- I. Launch a Zoom meeting and type “Happy Anniversary” in the meeting’s chat

Figure 15 - No "Tada" emojis rain down after typing "Happy Anniversary" in the meeting chat

- II. Type “Happy Anniversary” in a Zoom Team Chat

Figure 16 - "Tada" emojis rain down after typing "Happy Anniversary" in a team chat

3. **Description:** Hosts and co-hosts can rename meeting participants in the waiting room before they enter the meeting. After locating a participant's name in the waiting room section of the participant list, an option appears in the ... menu to rename that participant. The participant is notified of this change.

Category: **Incomplete NL** – The setting for allowing this feature must first be enabled in settings on the Zoom webpage

Source: [Highlighted Link](#)

Release: March 21, 2022 version 5.10.0 (4306)

Testing Steps:

- I. Start a meeting with a waiting room. Have another account join the meeting

Figure 17 - Before enabling the setting there is no ... menu to rename a person in the waiting room

- II. Enable the setting in the Zoom web browser. Relaunch the meeting and have another account join the waiting room.

Figure 18 – After enabling the setting there is a ... menu and an option to rename the person in the waiting room

4. **Description:** All participants in a meeting can view the participant attendance status. Previously, only the host and cohosts could view each participants' RSVP.

Category: **Incomplete NL** – The feature description doesn't specify the steps to enable this

Source: [Highlighted Link](#)

Release: January 16, 2023 version 5.13.5 (12053)

Possibly untestable (subscription-bound), needs calendar integration. There are also multiple ways to create a meeting & register.

5. **Description:** When a link to a private channel or message in a private channel is shared with a user that is not currently a member of that private channel, they can request access to join. The channel admin receives the request in that channel, and if approved, the requestor is notified of the approval.

Category: **Incomplete NL** – The feature description doesn't specify between accounts in same organization

Source: [Highlighted Link](#)

Release: September 26, 2022 version 5.12.0 (8964)

Possibly untestable (subscription-bound). It says other UC student accounts are external users and the two accounts must be in same organization. Need to try with another UC staff account.

6. **Description:** Users are shown a notification when they are added to a chat channel or group chat.

Category: **Ambiguous NL**– “Notification” is up to interpretation without a description

Source: [Highlighted Link](#)

Release: June 20, 2022 version 5.11.0 (6569)

Testing Steps:

- I. Create a channel

Figure 19 - The created channel

II. Add a different user to the channel

Figure 20 - The "notification" displayed as red dots

7. **Description:** Objects, or groups of objects, can be rotated during an in-meeting Whiteboard session. After clicking on the rotate icon, the option rotates, snapping to the nearest 15° increment. Holding the Shift key allows free rotation without snapping.

Category: **Incomplete NL** – Feature description just says to click; software only behaves on a click and drag

Source: [Highlighted Link](#)

Release: July 18, 2022 version 5.11.3 (7123)

Testing Steps:

- I. Launch Zoom meeting and open a whiteboard.
- II. Place an object or group of objects on the whiteboard.
- III. Rotate object/group of objects to be off axis. Single click. No snap back to 15 degree increment.

Figure 21 - Whiteboard object doesn't snap back to nearest 15 degree increment on a single-click

Figure 22 - Whiteboard object rotates on a click and drag

←-----CUTOFF LINE----->

8. **Description:** The Starred section has moved to the top on the sidebar, above all folders. A new caret menu to the right of the Chat title includes options to Create a Channel, Join a Channel, Create a Folder, and Add a Bot. The preview of unread Chats or Channels that appears when hovering over an unread badge on a collapsed folder or section will now include @all or @me mentions.

Category: **Ambiguous NL** – The phrase “Chat Title” could be the sidebar title or the title of a chat channel

Source: Highlighted Link

Release: June 20, 2022 version 5.11.0 (6569)

Testing Steps:

- I. Navigate to “Team Chat” page
- II. Open up the caret menu

Figure 22 – Opening the caret menu to the right of the sidebar title

9. **Description:** Hosts can get an idea of how active their breakout rooms are by viewing the list of open breakout rooms. Each participant in those breakout rooms will show their current video and audio status, if they are sharing their screen, and any active reactions or nonverbal feedback.

Category: **Ambiguous NL** – The phrase “Hosts can get an idea” is ambiguous

Source: [Highlighted Link](#)

Release: April 18, 2022 version 5.10.3 (4851)

Testing Steps:

- I. Create a meeting with other users

II. Create and start breakout rooms

Figure 23 - Breakout rooms created and users placed in a breakout room

III. Stay in the main session and look at active breakout room status

Figure 24 - The only way to gauge breakout room activity is a green dot signaling the user is connected to the breakout room

10. **Description:** Hosts and co-hosts are able to better manage breakout rooms with the ability to search for participants in breakout rooms by name, allowing them to quickly view, assign, or move participants between breakout rooms.

Category: **Ambiguous OR Incorrect NL** – Couldn't find search bar; POSSIBLY UNTESTABLE

Source: [Highlighted Link](#)

Release: June 20, 2022 version 5.11.0 (6569)

11. **Description:** When breakout rooms are created, the host can save that current configuration and participant assignments, which can be used in future sessions. This is only available for recurring meetings and limited to 10 saved configurations per user.

Category: **Incorrect NL** – Couldn't find how to save & reuse; POSSIBLY UNTESTABLE

Source: [Highlighted Link](#)

Release: March 21, 2022 version 5.10.0 (4306)

12. **Description:** Users can manage a central library of polls for meetings and webinars. They can create or edit polls and use them for Personal Meeting ID (PMI) and non-PMI meetings. Previously, polls for PMI and non-PMI meetings were managed separately. When a poll is marked as available to all meetings, it will appear in the list of polls that can be launched in a meeting. This new central repository will not replace the existing "Personal Meeting (PMI) polls", instead polls created here will only appear in PMI meetings.

Category: **Incorrect NL** – Couldn't find location for central polls; POSSIBLY UNTESTABLE

Source: [Highlighted Link](#)

Release: April 18, 2022 version 5.10.3 (4851)

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